

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Deliverable D6.1.(D12) Report on the list of fundamental model adjustments to better represent the solution space for EU agriculture to stay within the safe space

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation/acronym	Meaning
AGMEMOD	AGricultural MEmber State MODelling
BD30	BioDiversity strategy for 2030
BII	Biodiversity Intactness Index
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact Modelling System
CH4	Methane
CMEF	Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework
CO2	Carbon dioxide
CO2e	Carbon dioxide equivalents in terms of Global Warming Potential
EC	European Commission
EGD	European Green Deal
EU	European Union
EuroCARE	EuroCARE GmbH Bonn
F2FS	Farm to Fork Strategy
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FBI	Farmland Birds Index
FLINT	Farm Level Indicators for New Topics in Policy

GLOBIOM	Global Biosphere Management Model
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
IMAGE	Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment
INRAE	Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement
JOS	Just Operating Space
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
MAGNET	Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool
MIND STEP	Modelling INdividual Decisions to Support The European Policies related to agriculture
MS	Member State
MSA	Mean Species Abundance Index
N2O	Nitrous oxide
PB	Planetary Boundaries
PBL	Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving
PMEF	Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework
PROSA	PROgress towards Sustainable Agriculture
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SJOS	Safe and Just Operating Space
SOS	Safe Operating Space
Thuenen	Thünen Institute
UBO	University of Bonn
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore
UN	United Nations
WR	Wageningen Research
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable we describe the fundamental model adjustments, as described for task T6.1. The required fundamental model adjustments arise from the policy and technological options to address the safe operating space (SOS) for European Agriculture, and from the domains and indicators used to evaluate SOS outcomes. The fundamental model improvements are described here, by model and topic, in quite some detail, to facilitate exchange between models.

1. INTRODUCTION

The overall objective of the BrightSpace project is to design effective and sustainable strategies for assessing and addressing the challenges of EU agriculture to navigate within a safe and just operating space, including planetary boundaries as required by the European Green Deal. BrightSpace provides a set of analytical instruments to experiment, analyse, and coordinate the effects of innovative governance structures and policies related to agriculture to navigate within a Safe and Just operating space. These analytical instrument are combined in a set of computational models named the BrightSpace modelling toolbox (Figure 1).The BrightSpace modelling toolbox contains models from farm, to regional to global level, and varying detail in bio-physical or socio-economic detail (Figure 1), as also described in detail in D5.1. Further development of these models to address the Safe Operating Space is organized in WP6. Some of the model improvements are necessary to represent technological or policy options (WP8 and WP9) to stay within the Safe Operating Space (SOS), some are necessary to support the evaluation of indicators. To this end, we show here the SOS indicators selected and designed for BrightSpace (see also D1.1).

Figure 1 Models in the BrightSpace toolbox

The SJOS concept developed in BrightSpace follows the “Doughnut” concept proposed by Raworth (2012), which combines environmental, economic, and social aspects in a common framework. BrightSpace proposes a set of indicator domains to measure the progress towards or deviation from a Safe and Just operating space for EU agriculture by aligning established indicator frameworks for planetary boundaries (PB) and socio-economic boundaries with political objectives from the European Green Deal and the Common Agricultural Policy. This SJOS framework is discussed in deliverable D1.1. One objective of BrightSpace is to provide at set of indicators for the SJOS using the simulation models in the toolbox. With regard to the Safe operating space (SOS), the indicator domains considered and modelled are shown in Table 1. While a large variety of potential indicators of the SOS can already be calculated, some important aspects of the SOS are not yet fully covered and require adjustments and further developments of the toolbox models.

The subsequent section provide a model-by-model overview on the adjustments of the toolbox models to capture the needed indicators for the safe operating space (SOS) within the SJOS concept.

Table 1: BrightSpace Indicator domains and (example) indicators for the SOS (also presented in D1.1), and coverage by models

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Example Indicator(s)	Models
Biodiversity	Genetic/ Functional diversity (outcomes)	Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII)	IMAGE, GLOBIOM
		Terrestrial Mean Species Abundance (MSA) Farmland Birds Index (FBI) Fraction of remaining species (cSAR)	IMAGE CAPRI GLOBIOM
	Land management (drivers)	Agricultural area under organic farming	GLOBIOM (scen.), AGMEMOD (scen.), CAPRI (dev.), FARMDYN (scen.)
		Crop diversity index	GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD, CAPRI, FARMDYN
		Area in Agri-Environmental Measures (excl. organic farming)	GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD, CAPRI, FARMDYN
		Agricultural land covered with landscape features	CAPRI, FARMDYN (partly)
Land use	Land cover	Agricultural area (UAA)	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD, CAPRI, FARMDYN (scen.)
		Forest and other wooded land (FOWL)	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, , AGMEMOD (scen.), CAPRI
		Land cover (all other land cover types, including built-up areas, recreational area, ...)	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, , AGMEMOD (scen.), CAPRI
	Soil health	Tillage practices humus balance (drivers) crop yields (productivity)	FARMDYN (scen.)
Water use	Water use	Water abstraction in agriculture	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, MAGNET
		Irrigated land	IMAGE, GLOBIOM
Nutrient flows	Nitrogen cycle	Inorganic fertilizer Use Nitrogen Organic fertilizer application Nitrogen Gross nitrogen balance	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, CAPRI, FARMDYN

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Example Indicator(s)	Models
	Phosphorus cycle	Inorganic fertilizer Use Phosphorus Organic fertilizer application Phosphorus Gross phosphorus balance	IMAGE, CAPRI, FARMDYN IMAGE, CAPRI, FARMDYN IMAGE, GLOBIOM, CAPRI, FARMDYN
Chemical pollution (novel entities)	Pesticide use	Use of chemical pesticides	MAGNET, CAPRI, FARMDYN
		Use of more hazardous pesticides	CAPRI
	Antimicrobials	Use of antimicrobials in food producing animal	CAPRI (dev.)
Aerosol loading	Air pollution (Particulates)	Ammonia emissions	IMAGE, CAPRI, FARMDYN
Climate	Genetic/Functional diversity (outcomes)	GHG emissions agriculture, (CO ₂ e)	IMAGE, MAGNET, GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD (dev) CAPRI, FARMDYN
		Agr. Emissions - CO ₂ - CH ₄ - N ₂ O	IMAGE, MAGNET, GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD (dev.), CAPRI, FARMDYN

2. AGMEMOD

2.1. Organic farming - planned

The AGMEMOD team is developing a conceptual framework for organic farming that will serve as basis for implementing this new agricultural production type in the tool. The intention is to split total land allocation (per crop) over organic crop land use and conventional crop land use. Regarding livestock types, the herd will be split into herds confined to organic and conventional agriculture respectively. Consequently, the total market balance of a specific crop or animal product type is planned to be split into a market balance for organic farming and a separate market balance for conventional farming.

The conceptual framework starts with the description of the economics behind the markets of organic and conventional agriculture and their trade-offs in terms of e.g. land and prices. It also considers the factors that influence the markets, like supply drivers (technology, fertilizer and pesticide use), demand drivers (income, consumer preferences, population), policies and strategies (Green Deal, NSPs, organic land targets), and production factors (land constraints).

Next step will be to revise the current functional agricultural crop and livestock models in AGMEMOD and develop templates on functional equations for organic and conventional farming and its linkages that should be commonly applied in the country models. The land and herd splits will be specified as share functions explained by economy and policy variables. Hereafter, the AGMEMOD country databases will be revised and restructured in the sense that they must be extended with market balance data for both conventional and organic farming. The collection of data will be a challenging task here and requires close collaboration with the FarmDyn model that is built upon FADN data. Next steps in the implementation process will be to econometrically estimate all market and price variables at the MS level, to make projections for the future, to validate the results with market experts and

stakeholders, to revise AGMEMOD country models (if needed) and to make new projections. More details about conceptual and policy background of organic farming can be found in Annex 1, which also shows initial implementation steps as applied in AGMEMOD.

The intention is to test the approach at least for one crop market in a country or group of countries (e.g. wheat in the Netherlands and France) in Brightspace. However, at the end it will depend on the available capacity (in terms of budget) allocated to AGMEMOD modelling in Brightspace what can be done, also given other commitments and tasks to fulfill, like the implementation of the CAP.

3. CAPRI

3.1. Organic farming (T6.1) - ongoing

The CAPRI team has already compiled the member state-level database with differentiated organic and conventional activity levels, yields, gross production, output levels, and animal requirements. The activity levels and yields, consequently the gross production and output levels by organic and conventional activities have been further disaggregated to the NUTS2 level. The split of production activities into organic and conventional has required some major changes in the model. The first major adjustment in the model was the change of the set structure. This adjustment in the set structure is best demonstrated with the following example of the *set cere_cols* in the standard model version:

```
SET CERE_COLS "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition " /  
  
SWHE "Soft wheat production activity"  
DWHE "Durum wheat production activity"  
RYEM "Rye and meslin production activity"  
BARL "Barley production activity"  
OATS "Oats and summer cereal mixes production activity without triticales"  
MAIZ "Grain maize production activity"  
OCER "Other cereals production activity including triticales"  
  
/;
```

The *set cere_cols* is now disaggregated into three new sets: *cere_cols_std* (the standard set when the model is not run in organic mode), *cere_cols_org*, and *cere_cols_con* (for organic and conventional cereal activities, respectively):

```

SET CERE_COLS_STD "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition, standard" /

set.SWHE_std "Soft wheat production activity"
set.DWHE_std "Durum wheat production activity"
set.RYEM_std "Rye and meslin production activity"
set.BARL_std "Barley production activity"
set.OATS_std "Oats and summer cereal mixes production activity without triticale"
set.MAIZ_std "Grain maize production activity"
set.OCER_std "Other cereals production activity including triticale"

/;

SET CERE_COLS_ORG "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition, organic" /

set.SWHE_org "Soft wheat production activity, organic"
set.DWHE_org "Durum wheat production activity, organic"
set.RYEM_org "Rye and meslin production activity, organic"
set.BARL_org "Barley production activity, organic"
set.OATS_org "orgats and summer cereal mixes production activity without triticale, organic"
set.MAIZ_org "Grain maize production activity, organic"
set.OCER_org "orgther cereals production activity including triticale, organic"

/;

SET CERE_COLS_CON "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition, conventional" /

set.SWHE_con "Soft wheat production activity, coventional"
set.DWHE_con "Durum wheat production activity, coventional"
set.RYEM_con "Rye and meslin production activity, coventional"
set.BARL_con "Barley production activity, coventional"
set.OATS_con "Oats and summer cereal mixes production activity without triticale, coventional"
set.MAIZ_con "Grain maize production activity, coventional"
set.OCER_con "Other cereals production activity including triticale, coventional"

/;

```

Two additional sets are introduced/adjusted: **CERE_COLS_ALL**, containing all the aforementioned set elements,

```

SET CERE_COLS_ALL "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition, all" /

SET.CERE_COLS_STD "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition, standard"
SET.CERE_COLS_ORG "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition, organic"
SET.CERE_COLS_CON "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition, conventional"

/;

```

and the original **CERE_COLS** set is adjusted such that it contains the organic and conventional set elements when the model is run in organic mode and the standard (original) set elements when the model is run in the standard mode.

```

SET CERE_COLS "Cereals according to Grandes Cultures definition" /
$iftheni.org1 %organic% == ON
    SET.CERE_COLS_ORG
    SET.CERE_COLS_CON
$endif.org1

$iftheni.org2 %organic% == OFF
    SET.CERE_COLS_STD
$endif.org2

/;

```

In the database, the following consistency is maintained for the activity levels:

$$Act. Levels_{region,years}^{organic} + Act. Levels_{region,years}^{conventional} = Act. Levels_{region,years}^{standard}$$

To disaggregate the activity levels of organic and conventional activities from the member state level to NUTS2 levels, the shares of organic and conventional activity levels from the FADN data from 2000 to 2018 are used, and for Germany, the FSS data from 1999 to 2020 are used. However, since the data on activity levels at member state and NUTS2 levels come from different sources, the following consistency might be violated:

$$\sum_{Nuts2} Act. Levels_{Nuts2,years}^{organic} = Act. Levels_{MS,years}^{organic}$$

$$\sum_{Nuts2} Act. Levels_{Nuts2,years}^{conventional} = Act. Levels_{MS,years}^{conventional}$$

Thus, scaling factors for each activity, region, and year have been calculated, and the activity levels at the NUTS2 level have been multiplied by these scaling factors:

$$ScalingFactor_{Nuts2,years}^{act.} = \frac{Act. Levels_{MS,years}^{act.}}{\sum_{Nuts2} Act. Levels_{Nuts2,years}^{act.}}$$

The yield gaps at the NUTS2 level have been calculated under the assumption that the yield gaps at the NUTS2 level are equal to the yield gaps at the member state level. The next steps involve feed and fertilizer allocation to activities. The split of market balances will be addressed in a subsequent step following a feasibility study to explore options for splitting trade flows. Currently, it is anticipated that the complexities of the data may pose challenges for implementing such a split, but the feasibility assessment is still underway. In the absence of a full split of market balances, CAPRI will rely on assuming a certain markup for organic producer prices, thereby enabling disaggregation within the production sphere while treating products as homogeneous in markets.

3.2. The use of remote sensing data (from WP2) to refine regional data (T6.1) – planned

CAPRI primarily relies on Eurostat data from regional statistics and the farm structure survey to establish regional yields. However, these datasets often exhibit gaps for specific countries and regions or fail to comprehensively cover the list of activities outlined in the CAPRI database. Exploring the potential of grid-level datasets may offer a promising avenue to fill these gaps more effectively than previous approaches.

Moreover, grid-level data could provide insights into specific details of farmland use, for those that are partly supported by policy measures or outlined in the CAP Strategic Plans of Member States, such as landscape elements (hedgerows, ...) and catch crops. While current CAPRI data incorporates information from rural development programs for these farmland details if supported, it does not encompass "unsubsidized" landscape details. Therefore, aligning grid-level data from WP2 (and the LAMASUS project) has the potential to improve the database.

3.3. Pesticide application by crop and region (T6.2) - ongoing

Based on an earlier project, CAPRI has developed a methodology to allocate pesticide use, expressed in the quantity of active ingredients and disaggregated into 5 main groups: insecticides, herbicides, fungicides, growth regulators, and others, across regions and crops. However, this estimation requires verification and, potentially, revision. Efforts to further disaggregate this allocation to the level of (selected) single ingredients are still struggling with runtime problems and implausible results.

3.4. Biodiversity indicators - ongoing

The CAPRI team will contribute by establishing links from CAPRI outputs to GLOBIO or other biodiversity models covered by the planned interface.

Additionally, while no detailed plans or commitments have been made, the information exchange within this task will also be evaluated to explore potential calibration approaches for the existing CAPRI "biodiversity-friendly practices indicator." This evaluation may be undertaken within the framework of Brightspace or subsequent projects.

4. FARMDYN

4.1. Organic farming and environmental effects of technology and policy options (with WP8 & 9)

The bio-economic farm-level simulation model FarmDyn (Britz et al. 2016) covers several aspects relevant for the environmental dimensions of the SJOS. Nutrient flows and GHG emissions are part of the default reporting, as are indicators for biodiversity and land use. The following Table 2 provides an overview on the economic and environmental result indicators that can be calculated at farm level.

Organic farming activities are already specified in FarmDyn, but require additional data for farming operations, like quantities and prices for inputs applied in organic farming, yields and product prices, and potentially additional costs structures for machinery and buildings. Such data can to some extent derived from the EU-wide Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), which was requested during the first reporting period of the BrightSpace project and received in April 2024. This statistical database has been used in the past, e.g. in the context of the MIND STEP project, to create a FarmDyn model database for dairy and arable farms at NUTS2 level. Building on these experiences, FADN data will be split into fully converted organic and conventional farms and the differences in production patterns, area allocation, crop mix, land productivity, and so on, will be analyzed. Additionally needed datasets will be identified and acquired.

At the same time, FarmDyn permits the inclusion and testing of a wide range of technical and managerial options at farm level, as well as the inclusion of policy measures. The MIND STEP project has advanced the representation of GHG reducing technologies and grassland management options in FarmDyn (Helming et al. 2023, Krisztin et al. 2023). Further technology options will depend on the findings in WP8 regarding promising novel technologies.

	Item	Unit/Source	Crops	Livestock	Inputs	Farm	
Physical	Yield	t/ha	x				
	Level	ha or heads	x	x			
	Production	t	x	x			
	Sales	t	x	x			
	Labour	h	x	x		x	
	Nutrient needs	t	x	x		x	
	Nutrient supplies	t	x	x		x	
	Total feed use	t			x	x	
Monetary	Diesel	Euro	x		x	x	
	Seed	Euro	x		x	x	
	Purchased fertilizer	Euro	x		x	x	
	Pesticides	Euro	x		x	x	
	Purchased feed	Euro		x	x	x	
	Other variable cost	Euro	x	x		x	
	Total variable cost	Euro	x	x		x	
	Total allocable fix cost	Euro	x	x		x	
	Sales revenues	Euro	x	x		x	
	Gross margins	Euro	x	x		x	
	Fixed cost	Euro				x	
	Profits	Euro				x	
Emissions	CH4	Enteric fermentation				x	
		Pasture				x	
		Storage				x	
	N2O	Stable/Storage					x
		Indirect					x
		Pasture					x
		Fertilizer application					x
		Crop residuals					x
		Leaching					x
	CO2	Histosols					x
		Fertilizer application					x
		Purchased feed					x
	Total	CO2 equivalents					x

Table 2: Economic and environmental indicators of FarmDyn

4.2. Meaningful samples of farms to inform farm system representation in other models (WP2)

The FarmDyn model operates at the level of individual farms. In the model database, this can be individual farms, possibly observed from statistics, or constructed typical farms. In general, samples of typical farms are preferable to individual farms for pragmatic reasons (computation time and error resolving) as well as for the reason that a number of critical parameters are usually not available for individual farms, like data on field operations. The compilation of typical farms across the EU regions also improves the tractability of the results.

Building on the statistical analyses of the organic and conventional samples from FADN, a classification of typical farming systems for the EU will be proposed and aligned with comparable activities within the LAMASUS project. In particular the spatial distribution of these farming systems will be aligned with the land use maps used in LAMASUS.

5. IMAGE

5.1. Organic farming

As part of the updated representation of agricultural systems (see below), the IMAGE model (will distinguish organic agriculture next to conventional agriculture.

For the regional/national **production of organic commodities**, IMAGE will rely on MAGNET, which plans to distinguish organic and conventional commodities (see below) or extend current values into the future based on scenario assumptions. The difference in **yields for organic agriculture** will be based on literature reviews (e.g. Kravchencko et al. 2017). How to handle the **nutrient input in organic systems** is still under discussion. Spatial detail in nutrient application is one of the motivations to add more detail to IMAGE's land management representation (see below). For organic agriculture, sufficient nutrient supply is a challenge (Reimers et al. 2023), and relies on crop rotation, Nitrogen fixation, manure (preferably but not necessarily organic), but also on other external inputs like recycled fertilizers from urban waste. In a first step, we will build on IMAGE-GNM to allocate nutrient inputs (manure/fertilizer) to organic locations specifically. In terms of **agricultural management** on organic farmland, we will represent operations like tillage and residue management. For this, IMAGE is updating its internal LPJmL to version 5, allowing for explicit representation of those management options. As IMAGE represents cropland on a 5 minutes grid, the **spatial allocation of organic farming** needs to be addressed. For the starting situation, we (for EU scale). For allocation future organic systems, we explore whether the analysis of current organic agriculture allows to apply specific allocation principles for the future.

5.2. Representation of agricultural systems

Purpose: IMAGE is developing an updated representation of agricultural management, to better account for heterogeneity in space and between various agricultural systems. Amongst others, the purpose is to

- Analyse environmental effects in more spatial detail, and also to allow more spatial detail in analyzing safe space boundaries,
- Better reflect the impact on biodiversity,
- Improve the spatial representation of nutrient application and pesticides,
- Represent the effect of management practices on the carbon cycle (e.g. via tillage and residue management),
- Improve the feedback to the agro-economic system MAGNET.

Data: Based on the information collected in the “partner project” LAMASUS, we investigated which data are available. As global coverage is required, we will use the most recent version of the MapSpam database, plus some additional databases collected in the context of LAMASUS.

5.3. Updated model design (under development):

Gridded land cover and land use representation

- Add New Management Categories (independent of how we organize it)
 - High-input and low-input cropland based on MapSPAM
 - High-intensity and low-intensity grassland based on GLW (livestock); OR based on IMAGE's current livestock systems
 - Organic Farming
- Possible data structure:
 - agricultural grid cell contains, by crop/grass, the fraction of (i) irrigated, (2) high-input, (3) low-input, (4) organic, high-intensity grassland, low-intensity grassland.
- Possible allocation method (for scenarios):
 - Under development

Subregional detail:

For various processes, subregional detail *within* IMAGE-MAGNET region boundaries is important. For example, targets for organic farming will be likely realized on a national level, and dynamics of land-use change operate not freely within a region but are modulated by national (or local) circumstances. To add this sub-regional detail, we plan the following (under development).

- Use country and state/province (notably China, USA, India) data of crop production and land use area to allocate agricultural land use and production and to calibrate management factor and grazing intensity.
- Downscale agricultural production (and yield improvements) from MAGNET to subregion level for projections.

6. MAGNET¹

6.1. Implementation of Farm to Fork policies

MAGNET adjustments that have been made and are planned forward are related to the implementation of the Farm to Fork Strategy: increase the role of organic farming, reduce the use of environmentally unfriendly inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides (FF inputs further on) and to stimulate the role of agricultural R&D investments. Individual adjustments and modelling plans related to these topics are presented below.

6.2. Organic Farming

To effectively represent organic farming within MAGNET, a sector-splitting approach will be implemented. This will involve dividing relevant production sectors into separate conventional and organic sub-sectors. This detailed representation allows for variations in input use, land use, emissions

¹ The text on model improvements for MAGNET is slightly more detailed than the text for other models, as they are already more advanced in their implementation, and as this information is – in some cases – relevant for other models to plan their model development.

profiles, and other key factors between conventional and organic production systems. To parameterize the MAGNET model, the team will utilize data from both FADN (Farm Accountancy Data Network) and collaborations with the FarmDyn efforts.

We need, however, to acknowledge potential challenges associated with this approach. Data scarcity, particularly regarding organic farming practices, may necessitate a balance between detail and practicality. Input coefficient differences between organic and conventional systems will be carefully assessed, as these could require further model refinements. To maximize the impact and feasibility of the modeling, efforts will prioritize sectors where organic farming is most prevalent. Ongoing work in FarmDyn to develop farm typologies distinguishing organic and non-organic farms will greatly enhance the models' representativeness. Furthermore, the team is mindful of data aggregation needs to protect confidentiality, especially in regions with limited organic farms, and will explore strategies to address this without sacrificing model accuracy.

6.3. Pesticides sector

In order to better represent the environmental effects of technology, also based on the results of the simulations mentioned above, the MAGNET team has added the pesticides sector and pesticide products to the MAGNET base data. In the original version, pesticides were grouped under chemicals. Chemicals were therefore split into pesticides and the remaining chemicals. This was facilitated with data from Le Centre d'études prospectives et d'informations internationales (CEPII) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). The data from CEPII, known as the BACI data, contains data on bilateral trade flows for 200 countries at the product level (5000 products). The FAO data contains data on pesticide use in tons, per country. Specifying pesticides in the MAGNET database entails specifying the supply (production) and demand (use) per country of pesticides, as well as the international trade therein. The FAO data is used to determine the demand for pesticides. Doing so requires converting the tonnage in the FAO data to values by multiplying the tonnage by a price. The price is determined by the BACI data by taking the value of trade and dividing it by the tonnage. The BACI data also is used to determine the international trade itself. The supply (production) of pesticides per country is estimated as the use of pesticides minus the trade balance in pesticides. Finally, data on the tax and tariffs applied to the pesticides sector and products are derived proportionally from the chemicals sector.

This year, the pesticides data in the base data will be operationalized in the model. Specifically, this requires creating a parameterized production tree for the pesticides sector and inserting pesticides into the production trees of the agricultural sector. The aim is to facilitate substitution between pesticides and other factors of production. For example, it may be appropriate to allow substitution between pesticides and labor or pesticides and land. Appropriate elasticities of substitution must also be identified. In some cases, it may be more appropriate to assume that pesticides are required in a fixed proportion with other inputs. Once pesticides are operationalized in the model it will become possible to analyze the effects of policy on pesticide use per crop type at the country level.

Once this is operationalized, simulations can be done with respect to the reduction of pesticide use. However, as these are the high-risk pesticides that are harmful for the environment, while MAGNET incorporates all pesticides, further collaboration with other teams is needed to translate targets in terms of high-risk pesticide reduction to aggregate pesticide use reduction. Alternatively, data permitting, it could be possible in the future to make a further split of the pesticide sector on low-risk and high-risk pesticides, which would allow certain substitution between these two types of pesticides.

In addition, it will be important to link pesticide use to environmental indicators such as emissions (for now only emissions from fuel and fertilizer are modelled as input emissions in MAGNET). Later on, in the project, pesticide use in MAGNET could be linked to biodiversity indicators through IMAGE and GLOBIO.

A small piece of code has been implemented in MAGNET that allows to implement the required reduction of fertilizer and pesticide use for all agricultural sector via imposing shocks on inputs and redistributing them back as subsidies (see Annex 2).

6.4. Simulations on R&D investments and technological progress in MAGNET

While established empirical models of agricultural R&D (e.g. Alston, Huffman) assume long lags and neutral technical change, in relation to the changing focus of agricultural R&D programs (environmental goals), we investigated the role of reducing the R&D lag (speeding-up of technology transfer) and the role of changing R&D focus from yield maximization to input saving technologies (fertilizers and pesticides). The results sheds light on several aspects of sustainable productivity growth: what are the implications of new input saving technologies on food security and sustainability, ii) how reliable are our ex-ante projections when we do not reflect the newest technology developments in the modelling framework, iii) how environmental objectives can be most efficiently supported by R&D. The results of the simulations are included in two papers that will be presented at the upcoming ICABR conference in Ravello, June, 2024 (see Annex 1 and Annex 2).

There are still modelling adjustments needed to properly account for the changing R&D landscape. The first one deals with **adjusting R&D research lags** in line with the progress made in designing new gene technologies and also reflects the possible relaxation of strict regulatory processes in the EU. This requires reparametrizing the gamma distribution function that guides the process of converting agricultural R&D investments into productive R&D stocks. We incorporate the approval lag, g , in the weights of knowledge stock b_k following a gamma distribution (Alston et al., 2011). $b_k =$

$\frac{(k-g+1)\frac{\delta}{1-\delta}\lambda^{k-g}}{\sum_0^{LR}(k-g+1)\frac{\delta}{1-\delta}\lambda^{k-g}}$. Figure 2 shows the gamma distribution with different approval lags.

Figure 2. Gamma distribution with different approval lags. Source: Authors

Note: The choice of the optimal values for λ and δ for each region depends on the parameters that best fit the data in the empirical study (Kristkova et al., 2017). In Figure 2, we set $\lambda = 0.6, k = 0.8$ for illustration purposes.

The second adjustment is related to the way **how technologies save agricultural inputs**. In the established literature it is typically assumed that R&D investments have a neutral effect on productivity (they save all production factors – capital, labour and land). However, the recent technologies such as NGTs, biopesticides, etc. are oriented towards saving specific inputs. Sensitivity analysis where technological progress was redirected from neutral to saving fertilizers and pesticides in the EU showed that these assumptions can be quite crucial in terms of production volume impact

(10% growth vs 25% growth in 2020-2050 period) and use of F&F inputs (reduction of 24% vs increase by 4% in the same period). It is therefore crucial to have either empirically or expert validated evidence on the productivity impacts of the new promising technologies. This will be possible to obtain in collaboration with the WP8 (Task 8.1 – review of promising technologies). From these expert estimates, new promising technologies will be parametrized in MAGNET (such as NGTs or Artificial Intelligence) and be used in scenarios that simulate the uptake of technologies and their impacts on the SJOS.

6.5. Macro-economic principles in MAGNET (R&D, learning curves, investments, green finance) (based on WP3 and WP8)

To properly analyze the impact of policies relevant for the EU's agriculture, and in particular, the EU's Green Deal policies, the MAGNET model needs to be prepared to account for assets and liabilities associated with a country's wealth and capital stock and the relationship between investment and capital stock needs to be clearly defined, along with a robust investment determination mechanism that can generate long term reliable solutions when regional capital and wealth flows are altered.

Towards these ends, we conduct several substantial model developments around macroeconomic mechanisms including:

6.5.1. Wealth modelling

Many CGE models with explicitly introduced capital stock do not account for the accumulation of wealth. As such, there is no way to check the balance between capital stock and wealth in such models. Indeed, the benefits of wealth modelling are not just limited to a balance check between capital stock and wealth. An explicit modelling of wealth also makes it possible to account for foreign assets and liabilities that are meant to accrue separately to regional capital stock or to regional wealth, and thus contribute to regional income in a different way. Without accounting for these financial flows, a CGE model may exaggerate the benefits to countries that stimulate their investment and underestimate the benefits to countries of saving. Consequently, extra investment is never paid for and extra saving generates no future income (Dixon et al., 2019). Therefore, appropriate modelling of wealth is essential for an economy wide modelling framework especially when such a framework is intended for an investment-related Green Deal policy analysis.

In this research task, we introduce in MAGNET a wealth accumulation mechanism adapted from Dixon et al. (2019) which is further adapted from Ianchovichina & McDougall (2000). To allow for flexible calibration, we did a further operation for the capital stock accumulation equation implemented in Dixon et al. (2019) to decompose the total change in real wealth into two components: the first component captures wealth accumulated from saving in the absence of a change in annual saving throughout the multiannual period; and the second component captures the contribution to wealth accumulation due to a change in (real) saving. Representation of the second component is very meaningful. When the model runs annually with this equation, then the coefficient part collapses to 0, so the equation collapses to the first component which would be exactly the same as in the benchmark annual setting. This implies that we do not need two separate equations respectively for the annual setting (short run closure) and for the multiannual setting (long run closure) like in Dixon et al. (2019). Also, the existence of the second component with a coefficient multiplier enables us to calibrate saving growth to target certain desired real wealth growth rates through endogenizing the marginal propensity to saving defined in the model, and such a calibration cannot be implemented using the original equation in Dixon et al. (2019).

6.5.2. Investment and capital stock (see Annex 2 for more details)

In the previous standard version, the MAGNET model runs in multiannual steps, and capital growth in each region is set exogenously to follow the baseline GDP growth rate. While offering a succinct solution in capital determination and stable capital and investment movements across sectors and regions in usual model outcomes, this approach clearly has its weakness in assessing large-scale investment programs. Based on exogenously specified capital supply, this approach essentially disconnects the natural linkage between investment and capital endowment. Consequently, the specified capital growth may not be consistent with what is indicated by the equilibrium saving growth in the model.

As an improvement to the standard MAGNET approach, Smeets-Kristkova et al. (2021) established an explicit connection between investment and capital stock. In their approach, capital stock at the beginning of each projection period is derived from the accumulated investments over the preceding years. This improvement ensures a consistent transmission between investment growth and capital stock growth. However, the potential inconsistency between the multiannual results and the benchmark annual results remains and this inconsistency is caused by the so-called multiplication approach applied to capital stock accumulation, which is to some extent similar to the way capital stock is accumulated in GTAP-Dyn (Ianchovichina & McDougall, 2000).

To enhance the capital stock and wealth balance while maintaining the consistency with the benchmark annual results, we introduce in this research task a capital stock accumulation mechanism with smooth in-period growth for net investment. The proposed accumulation equation decomposes a change in capital stock into two parts: the first part capturing the constant investment carried over from Smeets-Kristkova et al. (2021) which represents the accumulation of capital stock in the absence of an in-period investment change; and the second part captures the contributions from any change in net investment. As shown in the model results, the added growth part for net investment ensures not only the consistency of capital stock accumulation compared with the benchmark annual results but also an enhanced balance with accumulated wealth globally. The functional form we introduce also allows for flexible calibration such that investment can be calibrated to target preferred capital growth rates.

6.5.3. Investment determination mechanism (see Annex 4 for more details)

In the MAGNET model which runs with the GTAP database and has the standard GTAP model in its core, regional investment is allocated through a virtual global bank where the savings collected from all regions is converted into investment which is then allocated across regions. With the global bank in place, there are two different ways to allocate investment across regions. One is the equalization of the expected rate of return across regions, and the other is the equalization of regional net investment growth rates. Under both approaches, however, we found that when running long term simulations, MAGNET may project volatile current accounts movements and unrealistic investment growth even in major economies. Consequently, agri-food projections may also be affected by these instabilities.

In this research task, an alternative investment determination mechanism will be introduced in the MAGNET core. In this new approach, regional banks are added to the model, along with the existing global bank, so the model will have a two-level banking system with segmented capital markets. With regional banks in place, investment will be able to connect directly with savings at the regional level. An important implication of this new approach is that investment growth at the regional level will be able to tap into the stability offered on the saving side as the growth in regional savings is bound by a Cobb-Douglas income allocation structure which in general behaves in a rather stable way. When regional investment and savings are explicitly connected, their respective domestic and foreign shares govern to what extent a stable change in regional savings will be reflected in the corresponding change in regional investment, a key stabilizer missing in the existing global bank approach. Clearly, this new

mechanism would offer a more systematic solution for the instability issue compared to using somewhat arbitrary swaps and assumptions as typically adopted in the past. The proposed mechanism also frees modelers from the hassle of having to calibrate the response parameters applied in deriving the expected rate of return.

7. GLOBIOM

7.1. Organic farming

The GLOBIOM team will represent organic farming as an explicit management system on the supply side though in a simplified manner (activity has just started). Productivities and economic costs will be based on literature or estimated using FADN data. The adoption of the organic system for the past period will be calibrated to national/EU statistics. No individual market representation for organic products is planned due to data limitations but a simplified tracing of products (organic vs. conventional as perfect substitutes) on the demand side is envisaged. Given the interlinkages with other modules, revisions of e.g. the nutrient accounting module or the biodiversity impacts assessment module, will need to be performed once the organic system is operational.

7.2. Representation of agricultural systems using remote sensing data and other databases

The GLOBIOM team will review and finalize the global representation of agricultural CO₂ sequestration practices with particular focus on the EU. So far, three carbon sequestration options on agricultural land have been added to GLOBIOM:

- Silvo-pasture systems for biomass and biochar production or carbon sequestration,
- Carbon sequestration through improved cropland and pasture management,
- Biochar application on cropland.

These agricultural practises were implemented as additional management system at the regional scale using data from biophysical modelling (Landsberg and Waring 1997) complemented by scientific literature (Lal 2006, Homagain, Shahi et al. 2016, Griscom, Adams et al. 2017, Roe, Streck et al. 2021) on carbon sequestration coefficients per technology, economic costs as well as information on the potential impact on crop- and pasture productivities. For the EU, we will review related mitigation potentials and economic costs and complement the dataset with so far absent, but relevant practises e.g. cover crops, hedges, and rewetting of organic soils.

Representation of grassland management systems will be revised to consider the restoration of degraded pastures using state-of-the-art remote sensing datasets from Copernicus, Corine Land Cover, Heathland maps, and other products (remote sensing data will become available within the LAMASUS project and possibly from WP2). The collected high level land use management data from LAMASUS & BrightSpace WP2 will allow to represent different grassland management intensities in GLOBIOM e.g. extensively managed semi-natural grassland systems, extensively managed pasture, intensively managed pasture, rough grazing and silvo-pastures.

7.3. GLOBIOM – FarmyDyn link

In MINDSTEP project we established a link from FarmDyn to GLOBIOM to parameterize a set of new add-on mitigation technologies for the livestock sector. This linking could be pursued in BrightSpace. FarmDyn team should indicate what they are interested to further explore.

7.4. GLOBIOM – water & nutrient modelling

The GLOBIOM team will improve the nutrient accounting module (Chang, Havlík et al. 2021) for the EU by substituting and aligning global datasets with better European data. This will improve the performance and consistency of the historical period (e.g., 2000-2020) at national and sub-national level with official statistics. Next to the revision of the N balances, representation of P will be included in the nutrient accounting module and in the output reporting. The N and P balances should account for differences in nutrient use efficiency across crops and crop production systems as well as for the local availability of manure by linking to the livestock module in GLOBIOM.

8. CONCLUSION AND THE NEXT STEPS

The list of fundamental model improvements above shows that some models are already quite far in the implementation process, while others are in the starting phase and busy with conceptual development. In some cases that is reflecting model interdependencies (e.g. MAGNET model providing data to IMAGE), and it also allows models to learn from others' experience. For the improved use of remote sensing data and new databases, model development was dependent on the availability of these data sources. Obviously, the models that are in the starting/conceptual phase (e.g. IMAGE, GLOBIOM), will further elaborate and implement their adjustments in the next 12 months. For all models, this inventory of fundamental model improvements is the starting point to exchange code and model documentation. In the coming 12 months, we will facilitate this exchange by monthly WP6 meetings with an in-depth presentation by one partner on the improved modelling.

9. REFERENCES

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# ANNEX 1: ABSTRACT SUBMITTED TO ICABR CONFERENCE, 2024 (MAGNET)

## **Assessing the Impact of Speeding Up R&D Transfer on Agricultural Productivity and Food Security**

Contribution Authors: Jin, Yan; Smeets Kristkova, Zuzana; Kardung, Max; Wessler, Justus

### **Context**

Postponing the adoption of technology is costly. The technology of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) has been technically available decades ago; however, its adoption has been limited due to political reasons resulting in lengthy regulatory process, which slows down the R&D transfer and affects agricultural productivity and food security.

### **Objective**

The objective is to assess the impact of speeding up R&D transfer on agricultural productivity and food security via comparing the projections of various indicators in status quo and those with a speed-up of R&D transfer due to simplification of the regulatory process of GMOs. We also consider several aspects of regulatory framework such as labelling costs and commercialization bans.

### **Method**

Our study incorporated a dynamic accumulation of R&D stocks including region-specific time lags and their links to agricultural productivity implemented in Modular Applied General Equilibrium Tool (MAGNET), a global computable general equilibrium model widely used for simulating the impacts of agricultural and land use policies at a macro level.

Due to simplification of the regulatory process, we assumed a left shift of the median of the distribution in the gamma distribution function of cumulated R&D stock while the evaporation of the R&D stocks remained at the same length. R&D investment in high-income regions exhibits long lags corresponding to the nature of the research. Developing regions were allocated to groups with short lags due to flexible adaptivity. Labelling costs were implemented by price margins and commercialization bans considered ban of NGT crops in food retail.

The baseline scenario considers GMO adoption according to the growth of R&D stock with the normal speed of R&D transfer and with additional labelling costs and commercialization bans in the EU. Alternative scenarios consider GMO adoption with a simplification of the regulatory process leading to a speed-up of R&D transfer.

### **Results**

Our study projected the impact of R&D transfer speed up and relaxation of regulatory framework on agricultural productivity and food security towards 2050. It also allows to assess important geopolitical consequences of regulatory framework adjustment.

### **Implications**

In line with the Farm to Fork strategy, speeding R&D transfer is one of the crucial preconditions for stimulating transition to sustainable agriculture. Simulations like this allow to understand the geopolitical consequences – namely the competitiveness of the EU vs USA and the role of NGT crops in reaching global food security.

## ANNEX 2: ABSTRACT SUBMITTED TO ICABR CONFERENCE, 2024 (MAGNET)

**Title: Sustainable productivity growth in agriculture: role of R&D investments and technology transfer**

Contribution Authors: Smeets Kristkova, Zuzana; M'Barek, Robert; Cui, David; van Dijk, Michiel; van Meijl, Hans; Ratinger, Tomas

### (1) Context

In connection to the recent slow-down of public agricultural R&D spending in high income countries (Fuglie and Heisey, 2018) and a shifting focus of public R&D from productivity maximization to environmental sustainability (Muscio and Sisto, 2020), questions emerge to which extent these developments will affect global food security and whether it is plausible to expect a coexistence of both sustainable and productive agriculture.

### (2) Objectives

This paper provides long-term projections of global food security under alternative assumptions of public agricultural R&D investment and their productivity impact. It builds on work of (Fuglie et al., 2022 and Villoria, 2019). While existing studies base their simulations on established empirical models of agricultural R&D (e.g. Alston, Huffman) assuming long lags and neutral technical change, this paper also investigates the role of reducing the R&D lag (speeding-up of technology transfer ) and the role of changing R&D focus from productivity maximization to input saving technologies (fertilizers and pesticides) in agriculture.

### 2 Methodology

The paper applies CGE model MAGNET (Woltjer and Kuiper, 2012). In MAGNET, public agricultural R&D investments are linked to R&D sector (assuring that R&D creation uses productive resources) and converted to agricultural R&D stocks. The increase in R&D stocks subsequently leads to factor-augmenting technical change. To operationalize R&D module in MAGNET, a global R&D database has been compiled with international comparable data on agricultural R&D expenditures and number of research staff covering the period 1960-2019.

### (3) Results

Global agricultural emissions (2020-2050) are projected to grow quicker (+50%) than the output (+40%). The persistent growth in emissions suggests that global agricultural sector may not stay within the safe operating space. Plotting agricultural productivity growth and emissions shows an upward sloping curve. Higher R&D investment growth can reduce the slope but doesn't alter the sign. When considering potential shifts in the direction of R&D-driven technical change in agriculture from neutral to input saving, productivity growth can become sustainable. Speeding-up of R&D transfer can avoid the projected decline of agricultural R&D stocks, productivity and output in this decade and in long-term it makes the impacts of technologies more pronounced however, direction of technical change is more impactful than speed-up of R&D transfer.

### (4) Implications

Sustainable productivity could be a feasible prospect for high income countries if R&D programs significantly change their focus and speed up technology transfer. New empirical evidence is needed to quantify the impact of promising technologies on productivity.

## ANNEX 3: ABSTRACT SUBMITTED TO GTAP CONFERENCE 2024 (MAGNET)

**Title: A consistent and balanced approach to capital stock accumulation in multiannual recursive dynamics**

Contributing authors: Hao David Cui, Zuzana Smeets Křístková, Hans van Meijl, Bartłomiej Rokiki, and Antti Simola

Recursively dynamic computable general equilibrium (CGE) models are widely used for policy analysis including assessments of policy initiatives with a focus on investment (e.g. the European Green Deal with a trillion Euro investment budget). In these modelling exercises, the mechanism of capital stock accumulation plays a very important role due both to the inherently close relationship between (public, private, or green) investment allocations and capital stock formation and to the recursively dynamic nature of the baseline itself where capital stock accumulation acts as one of the key drivers of macroeconomic growth. Given the potential dual role of capital stock in a baseline and investment scenarios, it is thus crucial to construct a model with a capital stock accumulation mechanism that is well-behaved and model-wide consistent.

CGE models with capital-driven recursive dynamics may run in time steps of varying lengths. While annual steps are probably the first choice for the majority of CGE modellers, there exist at least several large and complex models usually run in multiannual steps, such as ENVISAGE (Van der Mensbrugghe, 2008), GEM-E3 (Capros et al., 2013), MIT EPPA model (Chen et al., 2022) and d-PLACE (Gaska et al., 2020). If a CGE model is specified to be multiannual (i.e., more than one year in each step/period), questions may arise as to whether such a specification can still yield capital growth projections consistent with its counterpart running in annual (year on year) steps, and whether the accumulated capital stock and wealth (accumulated from net savings) are still in balance globally. This is because once a model becomes multiannual, the projected capital growth would be sensitive to how capital stock is (assumed to be) accumulated throughout the years in each period. Depending on the specified mechanism, the latter may or may not differ significantly from the benchmark annual simulations.

While models can be set up in annual steps to avoid such problems (at least for the consistency with annual results), and many economic models are indeed run in annual steps, there are good reasons for some models to be run in multiannual steps rather than in annual steps. First, running in multiannual steps can significantly reduce the time required to solve a model and this especially matters for very large and complex computable general equilibrium models. If running in annual steps, a large CGE model with a multi-dimensional data structure that includes many sectors and regions can take hours or even days to solve in order to produce decades-long annual projections. However, if the same model runs, say, in ten-year steps instead of annual steps, then the time required to run the model would be significantly shortened – to about a tenth of the time if running annually. Taking also into account that models usually need to run several times for debugging, this type of multiannual setting would naturally be a time-efficient choice for modellers. Second, the reporting requirements usually prefer model results to be presented for some milestone years such as 2030, 2040, 2050, etc., rather than for all individual years into the far future. Setting models up in multiannual periods with each period ending at these milestone years enables modellers to make efficient use of research time by skipping those years in between while still meeting the reporting requirements. Third, data availability sometimes may also limit a model's capacity in handling a higher time-resolution. A model baseline constructed upon assumptions across multiple social, economic, and environmental domains may require data inputs from various sources. Some of these sources may not have sufficient data available for all the years exactly matching the baseline setup. In this situation, modellers may have to make certain assumptions and apply the same data to a number of years and run the model in multiannual steps to wrap up those years in a single time step.

For the above reasons, some large and complex dynamic models may prefer to run in multiannual rather than in annual steps, and as such, these models may suffer from the aforementioned potential issues of inconsistency and imbalance, if multiannual periods are applied. Among widely used CGE models for policy analysis, MAGNET features recursive dynamics with a multisectoral and multiregional coverage (Woltjer et al., 2014), with the model core built upon the standard GTAP modelling framework (Hertel, 1997; Corong et al. 2017). In the default standard version, the model runs in multiannual steps, with capital growth in each region simply following GDP growth in the region. While offering a succinct solution in capital determination and stable capital and investment movements across sectors and regions in usual model outcomes, this approach clearly has its weakness in assessing large-scale investment programmes. A good example of such programmes is the European Green Deal investment plan, which is meant to spend around 25% of EU budget on environmental objectives until 2030 (European Commission, 2020). Based on exogenously specified capital supply, this approach essentially disconnects the natural linkage between investment and capital endowment. Consequently, the specified capital growth may not be consistent with what is indicated by the model via the equilibrium savings growth. In other words, economic growth under such a model specification may be sustained by underestimated or overestimated capital growth rates, which, in turn, may cause unreasonable levels of technological change across model regions due to the inherent relationship between technical change and capital growth in the baseline calibration.

As an improvement to the standard MAGNET approach, Smeets-Kristkova et al. (2021) established an explicit connection between investment and capital stock. In their approach, capital stock at the beginning of each projection period is derived from the accumulated investments over the preceding years. This improvement ensures a consistency between investment growth and capital stock growth. Simulation outcomes show that the resulting dynamic trajectories are largely supported by historical observations as indicated in the Penn World Table (Feenstra et al., 2015). However, the potential inconsistency with the benchmark annual results remains and this issue lies in the approach applied to capital stock accumulation. In each multiannual step, capital stock is accumulated through multiplying the corresponding base year (net) investment with the number of years in that multiannual step. This approach is similar to the way capital stock is accumulated in GTAP-Dyn (Ianchovichina & McDougall, 2000) when multiannual steps are applied. As shown later, this multiplication mechanism may cause inconsistent capital growth when compared to the benchmark annual (i.e. year-on-year) simulation results. Moreover, if the wealth flows are not explicitly modelled, there is still a potential inconsistency between the derived capital stock and the capital stock indicated from the savings side of the model, since in such case no balance check can be given to the accumulated capital stock. Therefore, simulation outcomes may exaggerate the benefits for countries that act as net investors and underestimate the benefits for net lenders (Dixon et al., 2019; Dixon et al., 2021; Lemelin et al., 2013).

To address the consistency and balance issue in MAGNET's multiannual setting, we first introduce a wealth accumulation mechanism adapted from Dixon et al. (2019) which would yield consistent wealth accumulation in multiannual steps and offer flexibility to calibrate saving growth for given wealth accumulation trajectories. We then discuss and compare alternative capital stock accumulation mechanisms which would yield a balance and the consistency to varying degrees. Apart from the constant in-period investment approach as mentioned above, we also discuss the GTAP-Dyn approach which allows for investment being updated in a multistep model solution. We show that this approach is similar to the linear investment growth approach as both types of assumptions lead to a bit overshooting results. We then present the smooth growth approach for both gross investment and net investment. With detailed mathematical expositions supported by test simulations, we show that the smooth in-period net investment growth produces the best balance and consistency among all multiannual settings.

## ANNEX 4: ABSTRACT SUBMITTED TO GTAP CONFERENCE 2024 (MAGNET)

### Title: An investment determination mechanism with segmented capital markets

Contributing authors: Hao David Cui and Zuzana Smeets Křístková

In the standard GTAP model as well as in the MAGNET model which runs with the GTAP database and has the standard GTAP model in its core, regional investment is allocated through a virtual global bank where the savings collected from all regions is converted into investment which is then allocated across regions subject to an equalization of expected rates of return for all regions. If we combine the associated equations for the expected rates of return equalization, the determination of regional expected rates of return, and the relationship between end-of-period capital stock, start-of-period capital stock and investment, we may derive one combined equation to express regional investment growth as the function of regional capital stock growth and the relative change between the globally equalized expected rate of return and the regional current rate of return, with the relative change being multiplied by a combined coefficient consisting of the reciprocals of the response parameter, RORFLEX, and the ratio of gross investment in end-of-period capital stock, INVKERATIO.

In this combined equation, we can see that a key to investment determination is to calibrate an appropriate response parameter, RORFLEX, as it affects not only how the expected net rate of return (expected rate of return relative to current rate of return) responds to investment, but also the relative movement between investment and capital stock. As a key component on the expenditure side of macroeconomic growth, investment growth will undoubtedly have large implications for the movements in the other macroeconomic components. In particular, since private consumption and government consumption are tied to a Cobb-Douglas structure of regional income allocation, changes in these two macroeconomic components are expected to be rather stable. Consequently, this may leave the current accounts more responsive to a change in investment. If the value of the response parameter is too low, which is indicative of a large investment change, we might end up having volatile responses in current accounts. On the other hand, if the parametric value is too high, investment growth may be forced to follow capital stock growth closely causing a homogenized growth mode across regions which may also lead to an undesired trade-off between investment and current account and some other inconsistencies. This is because, first, regions may differ significantly in the macroeconomic growth mode as indicated to a certain degree in the base data structure; second, in a dynamic model, the relationship between investment and capital stock is already determined in the capital stock accumulation equation where capital stock is accumulated from investment in a natural way, which implies that it does not make a lot of sense having two equations in the model to determine the relationship between the same pair of variables, and third, inconsistencies may also be reflected in potentially large relative (or even opposite) movements between the expected rate of return and the current rate of return.

We conduct a number of MAGNET baseline experiments using different values for the response parameter. When using the default value of 10, we find that investment in many regions shows rather aggressive growth, causing very negative responses in the current account in these regions. For example, investment in North America (US and Canada) barely changes over the 30+ projection years, which has to be compensated by an extreme shift in the current account balance (from a large negative to an extremely large positive) in order to sustain the assumed macroeconomic growth. China's total export collapses with a negative growth rate below -20% or even -30% over three ten-year periods, which turns China's current account balance from a large positive number to hugely negative numbers. If the parametric value is increased to 100, regional investment growth is seen moving closer with capital stock growth, which is as expected, but this also causes inconsistencies reflected through the trade-off between investment and current account and the relative change in

the expected and current rates of return. For instance, investment growth in the EU becomes unrealistically high, even higher than the assumed GDP growth, implying that EU's growth mode shifts from consumption-led to investment led. This causes a sharp decline in its current account contributed to mostly by soaring import which is projected to increase about eight times over a ten-year period. Inconsistencies are also reflected in the opposite movements between the expected rate of return and the current rate of return worldwide over several ten-year periods in a row, which indicates that investors constantly make biased decisions over the long-term investment allocation.

Our experiments show that it can be very difficult to get a sound response parameter that can lead to reasonable projections particularly for a balanced trade-off between investment growth and the current account balance. The results also indicate that this parameter may need to be region-specific and even period-specific since the same parameter leading to a reasonable trade-off during certain projection periods cannot be guaranteed to also lead to reasonable trade-offs in the other periods. Due possibly to knowing this calibration difficulty, the standard GTAP offers another option to allocate regional investment which is the equalization of net investment growth rates across regions. As can be imagined, forcing net investment in all regions to grow at the same pace may also lead to undesired results. With this mechanism switched on, for example, North America will experience very high investment growth leading to very negative current account balances with the overall deficit by 2050 expected to be over five times its 2017 level. EU's total import will also be unexpectedly high over a ten-year period. While dramatic movements in current accounts reflected through changes in export and/or import are possible in real world, these movements are usually caused by factors (e.g. a new regional trade agreement) that cannot be explained by the model. In other words, without introducing any exogenous shocks reflective of a significant policy shift, it is hardly convincing to project a dramatic change in an otherwise general model baseline.

One possible way out to solving these issues associated with the current investment determination mechanisms offered in standard GTAP is to exogenously fix the current account balance or let the current account components (export, import, or both) follow certain existing trends (e.g. GDP growth) in troubling regions. While this may help bring investment growth back to a normal track, one has to admit that this is a rather patchy way than a systematic approach to fixing issues since additional assumptions may need to be made as to how the model would accommodate to such an exogenous shift in the current account. This calibration procedure usually requires a swap with another exogenous variable in the model such as a productivity change variable or a preference shifter. Such swaps may not work in all the situations as the model solved this way may have particular requirements for the structure of the base data. In certain regions especially some smaller regions, data quality is often an issue so a seemingly regular swap can unintentionally lead to a crash of the model, which has been experienced multiple times in our baseline experiments.

In this paper, we introduce an alternative investment determination mechanism in the MAGNET core (i.e. the standard GTAP) to replace the existing approach of the equalization of the expected rate of return. In this new approach, regional banks are added to the model, along with the existing global bank, so we now have a two-level banking system with segmented capital markets. With regional banks in place, investment will be able to connect directly with savings at the regional level. This connection clears the capital market in each region where the domestic and foreign sources of investment and savings are distinguished using financial flows data available from MAGNET's wealth module. Since the expected rate of return is not required anymore to equalize across regions, the existing equations associated with the expected rate of return only work as non-essential summary equations. An alternative mechanism is established in the regional price linkage between investment and savings where an endogenous scalar variable is introduced to equalize the relative price change between investment and savings across regions and capture the Walras's law, a role played previously by the global expected rate of return. We interpret this mechanism as an equalization of risk premium across regions.

An important implication of the new investment determination approach is that investment growth at the regional level will be able to tap into the stability offered on the savings side as growth in regional savings is bound by a Cobb-Douglas income allocation structure which in general behaves in a rather stable way. When regional investment and savings are explicitly connected, the domestic and foreign shares govern to what extent a stable change in regional savings will be reflected in the corresponding change in regional investment, a key stabilizer missing in the existing expected rate of return equalization approach. This important implication has been confirmed with the updated simulation results where the abovementioned issues disappear not only in those major economies but also in smaller regions. Clearly, this new mechanism would offer a more systematic solution for the trade-off issues without having to resort to any patchy swaps and additional assumptions. Compared to the existing approaches, the proposed mechanism also frees modelers from the hassle of having to frequently calibrate the region-specific and possibly period-specific response parameter which can be a daunting task in a typically time-consuming baseline experiment.

# ANNEX 5. MODELLING ORGANIC AGRICULTURE IN AGMEMOD (DETAILED)

## Introduction

**BRIGHT SPACE**

**Outline**

- Introduction
- Some economics of organic agriculture
- Policy and organic agriculture
- Modelling approach
- Modelling in AGMEMOD
- Derived indicators
- Concluding remarks
- References

**BRIGHT SPACE**

**Introduction (3)**

- Kremmydas et al. (2023)...
  - analyse the impacts of the F2F target of 25% organic farmland by 2030 by means of the IFM-CAP model
  - explore two different adoption patterns
    - endogenous – farm conversions to organic production result from assessing the utility difference between organic and conventional production systems
    - exogenous – relies on econometric estimation of the likelihood of farms to convert to organic driven by a combination of monetary and non-monetary drivers
  - find that different adoption patterns lead to differences on the outcomes
    - gross income changes are in the range of +3.8% (endogenous case) to -1.3% (exogenous case)
  - estimates declines in production (-0.5% to -15%) for most crops and animal products when achieving the target (regardless the adoption pattern)

**BRIGHT SPACE**

**Introduction (4)**

- Krajewski et al. (2024)...
  - analyse the evolution of organic farming in the EU over the period 2004-2021, with a focus on the evolution of preferences and priorities of farmers and consumers
  - find that production level of organic products exhibit negative correlations with human population density, GDP per capita and the human development index (HDI)
  - report that Baltic countries and Austria led in organic farming production, while countries such as Malta, the Netherlands, Belgium, Ireland, and Luxembourg are lagging in terms of organic production per capita
  - indicates that the achievement of a 25% share of organic agriculture in unlikely in most EU countries by 2030 (based on linear regression/projections of past trends). Austria, Estonia and Sweden are the only countries which could achieved the target in this context
  - concludes that additional efforts/further support are needed to achieve the expected target by 2030

**BRIGHT SPACE**

**Introduction (1)**

**Facts and figures**

**BRIGHT SPACE**

**Introduction (2)**

- Lampkin and Sanders (2022) highlight that...
  - in the EU, organic agriculture has been supported by means of agri-environmental and rural development measures (2nd Pillar of the CAP)
  - the first scheme to support organic farming was implemented in Denmark in 1987, with additional schemes following in Austria and Sweden
  - in 2018, EU28 MS supported organic farming on almost 5% of EU utilisable agricultural area (UAA) – this is equivalent to 64% of total EU certified organic land. The financial support provides was around €207 per ha UAA
  - specific measures: (a) Organic area payments; (b) Other agri-environmental measures; (c) Other rural development support; (d) Other nationally or regionally supported measures; (e) National or regional organic action plans; (f) Future outlook for organic support.
  - despite financial support farmers might be discouraged to practise organic farming if market conditions do not fully remunerate their efforts

## Economic and policy background of organic farming

**BRIGHT SPACE**

**Some economics of organic agriculture**

- See PPC figure: there is a (negative) trade-off between organic (o) and conventional (c) agriculture (in terms of land, and more so in terms of production volume)
- A change in relative prices (P) is a key economic variable explaining switch to organic, with P including output prices (price premium) as well as input prices (e.g. organic feed) and acting like a (relative) margin indicator

**BRIGHT SPACE**

**Policy and organic agriculture**

- **Transition funding: one time; easing transition period**
  - Support for maintenance and conversion to organic farming is available in almost all EU countries since the 1990's
  - T-funding: effectiveness depends mainly on the coverage of on-time transition costs
  - NSPs define the most recent targets and efforts at MS-level
- **Action Plans**
  - Focus especially on demand 'development', which effect will be implicitly shown in terms of market demand and prices
- **NSP and relevant indicator**
  - Key indicator is R8 share of organic agriculture (land)
  - Both current estimates, target values, and reported values are/will become available

## Modelling approach

### Modelling approach (1)

- Add-on modelling (refine choices/land allocation on top of 'totals' as they are modelled already now, with a focus on supply (for the moment))
- Approach**
  - For crops and grazing animals: use a land-based approach (estimate share of land confined to organic agriculture)
  - For (land-lose) intensive livestock: use a herd (estimate share of herd confined to organic agriculture)
- Follow a share function methodology**
  - Choose a proper specification (e.g. probit, logit)
  - Choose explanatory variables (price ratios, policy) as economic driver
  - Account for nature of structural/investment decision (e.g. lagged vars, adjustment costs)
  - Take impact of policy measures into account

### Modelling approach (2)

- Proposal to follow a logistic regression as the dependent variable is [0, 1]
  - Follow logit model
    - $\ln \frac{p_o/p_c}{1 - p_o/p_c} = c + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + c Z$
    - $p_o = \dots$
    - $p_c = \dots$
  - $p_o$  : probability of farm being organic
  - $p_c$  : probability of farm being conventional
  - $X_i$  : price and cost ratio's
  - $Z$  : policy variable
- Info needed:
  - price; and
  - cost ratio's (or relative gross margins)
- Note that probability can be 'translated' into shares (of areas, herds)

Organic farming modelling in AGMEMOD – first steps

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (1)

A stylized application in AGMEMOD

- Current situation in AGMEMOD
  - crop, dairy and meat commodity markets reflect a hybrid form of conventional and organic farming
- Experiment: specify organic farming in AGMEMOD model via
  - a stepwise approach (stylized)
  - the case of wheat in the Netherlands



### Modelling in AGMEMOD (2)

From data collection to projection & visualisation



### Modelling in AGMEMOD (3)

Step 1: define conceptual framework of organic crop farming

- Understand the organic farming sector:
  - How does the sector look like? Which market players? Which mechanisms? Which policy (national, EU)? Role of the world? Which drivers? Which competing crops? Price (premiums)?
- Develop flow chart for organic crop farming, example soft wheat in the Netherlands:
  - Build on standard crop template used in AGMEMOD
  - Build on land allocation tree used in AGMEMOD
  - Replicable to all countries and years




### Modelling in AGMEMOD (4)

Step 1a: Determine country module for organic wheat farming



Basic structure for organic wheat farming (OWS\_)

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (5)

Step 1b: Land allocation: split soft wheat area into organic wheat area & conventional wheat area



Share of conventional soft wheat area in total soft wheat area:  $CWS\_ASH = 1 - OWS\_ASH$   
 CWS : Mnemonic for conventional wheat commodity

Share of organic soft wheat area in total soft wheat area (OWS\_ASH) is determined by: policy targets, returns, trends  
 OWS\_ : Mnemonic for organic wheat commodity

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (6)

Step 2: Define a simple functional model for organic wheat farming

KEY functional equations for estimation

- $OWS\_PRN$ : producer price of organic wheat  
 = f(key price (+), self-sufficiency rate (-))
- $OWS\_ASH$ : share organic wheat area harvested in total wheat area  
 = f(policy target (+), expected returns organic/conventional (+), trend)
- $OWS\_YHA$ : yield/ha of organic wheat  
 = f(costs organic/conventional (-), trend)
- $OWS\_UPC$ : consumption/capita of organic wheat  
 = f(own price (-), cross price (+), income (+))



### Modelling in AGMEMOD (7)

**Step 3: Data collection and mapping**

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (8)

**Step 3a: Collect data for setting up the organic wheat model**

- Data collection for all organic wheat market variable in templates (see right side) in historical period for each country:
  - Production, food use, feed use, imports and exports (1000t)
  - Area harvested (1000 ha)
  - Prices, production costs (euro/100 kg)
- Policy variables in historical period for each country:
  - Target area allocated to organic wheat farming (%)
  - CAP budgetary support
- Drivers:
  - Macroeconomic: world prices, inflation rate, gdp, population, exchange rate

Sources: e.g. EUROSTAT, FAO, national statistics, FADN, farm type models, EC policy reports, technical and market studies, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&code=sdg-12.2>

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (9)

**Step 3a: Collect data for setting up the organic wheat model on input costs (per unit of output)**

Organic crop vs conventional crop production, some FADN based differences:

- /- 75-100% on plant protection costs/ha; -/ 45-90% on fertilizer costs/ha; more labour intensive
- Costs/ha in FR and DE higher; lower in AT, IT, PL
- Yield/ha gap for wheat is 30 to 50% (e.g. FR: 48%)
- Organic wheat price is about twice as high (premium on producer price to bring organic price to conventional price; e.g. 21% in FR)
- Organic support payment in EU ca. 144eur/ha CAP support, and 79eur/ha national co-finance

**Table 2.1 - Input costs per unit of economic output, income per worker, and labour per unit of economic output in organic versus conventional plant production farms in selected countries<sup>1</sup>**

|                                    | Belgium | France | Germany | Italy | Spain | UK  |
|------------------------------------|---------|--------|---------|-------|-------|-----|
| Conventional wheat production      | 1.1     | 1.1    | 1.1     | 1.1   | 1.1   | 1.1 |
| Organic wheat production           | 1.1     | 1.1    | 1.1     | 1.1   | 1.1   | 1.1 |
| Income per worker                  | 1.1     | 1.1    | 1.1     | 1.1   | 1.1   | 1.1 |
| Labour per unit of economic output | 1.1     | 1.1    | 1.1     | 1.1   | 1.1   | 1.1 |

Source: Based on EU FADN - 2017-2020 data (2020 preliminary data).  
<sup>1</sup> Exceptions: slightly lower in 3 out of 14 country x economic size combinations  
<sup>2</sup> Exceptions: slightly higher in 2 out of 14 country x economic size combinations  
<sup>3</sup> Exceptions: slightly higher in 1 out of 14 country x economic size combinations  
<sup>4</sup> Exceptions: slightly lower in 2 out of 14 country x economic size combinations

Economic, technical and policy support conditions differ per country

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (10)

**Step 3a: Collect data for setting up the organic wheat model on consumer perception/preferences**

Consumer's main drivers for buying organic food:

- Nutritious and healthy, no use of synthetic pesticides, affordability of food for all, better animal welfare
- Affordability is a key factor in developing demand for organic products (inflation rate, slow economic growth)

Percentage organic food sales in total sales:  
 - e.g. NL: stabilizes around 3%

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (11)

**Step 3b: Implement (preliminary) organic wheat data in NL-datagemod\_base.xls**

- Add new lines for each market variable and add data in 'database' sheet. Check LAYOUT range!
- Check balance consistency (prod+imp-exp=0)

### Modelling in AGMEMOD (12)

**Step 3c: Implement data on organic wheat area target in Assumptioninput\_baseline.xls**

Add new lines for policy minimum area targets and add data in CC\_policy sheet. Check LAYOUT range!

**WPOLC: Minimum organic wheat land in F2F**

|                                                            | 2020 | 2021 | 2022 | 2023 | 2024 | 2025 | 2026 | 2027 | 2028 | 2029 | 2030 |
|------------------------------------------------------------|------|------|------|------|------|------|------|------|------|------|------|
| Minimum share organic wheat land for new CAP 1,000 ha OWS_ | 0.01 | 0.02 | 0.03 | 0.05 | 0.12 | 0.16 | 0.19 | 0.24 | 0.31 | 0.35 | 0.35 |
| Minimum share organic wheat land for new CAP 1,000 ha OWS_ | 0.01 | 0.02 | 0.03 | 0.05 | 0.09 | 0.12 | 0.16 | 0.19 | 0.24 | 0.25 | 0.25 |

**CC\_policy sheet in Assumption\_baseline.xls (country dependent minimum targets):**

- Policy target to achieve until 2030: min. 30% of wheat area under organic farming (gradual path assumed)
- New activity mnemonic:
  - ASH\_MIN: minimum share of organic wheat area in total wheat area

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## ANNEX 6. IMPLEMENTATION OF F&F TARGETS IN MAGNET

A small piece of code has been implemented in MAGNET that allows to implement the required reduction of fertilizer and pesticide use for all agricultural sector via imposing shocks on inputs and redistributing them back as subsidies.

The shocks can be applied on total use and the model can endogenously determine optimum reduction of the FF inputs per agricultural sector.

Equation `E_qfa_ff` calculates aggregate use of FF inputs (c) across all agricultural sectors (a):

Equation `E_qfa_ff`

# weighted average over individual agri-sector uses #

`(all,c,COMM)(all,r,REG)`

`qfa_ff(c,r) = sum[a, ACTS, shVFP_ff(c,a,r)*qfa(c,a,r)];`

Equation `E_del_Vtfa_ffA` determines total collected taxes from use of the FF sensitive inputs:

Equation `E_del_Vtfa_ffA`

# Abs change in domestic tax revenue from ff targets #

`(all,a,AGRI_ACTS)(all,r,REG)`

`100*del_Vtfa_ff(a,r)=`

*!Tax income from domestic purchases!*

`sum[c, COMM, VDFP(c,a,r)*tfa_ff(c,a,r)] + sum{c, COMM,`

`VDFP(c,a,r)*[pds(c,r) + qfd(c,a,r) + tfd(c,a,r)+if{a in fuelsect, tfdghg(c,a,r)}]`

`- VDFP_basff(c,a,r)*[pds(c,r) + qfd(c,a,r) + tfd(c,a,r) +if{a in fuelsect, tfdghg(c,a,r)}]}`

*!Tax income from import purchases!*

`+ sum[c, COMM, VMFP(c,a,r)*tfa_ff(c,a,r)]+ sum{c, COMM, VMFP(c,a,r)*[pms(c,r) +`

`qfm(c,a,r) + tfm(c,a,r) +if{a in fuelsect, tfmghg(c,a,r)}]`

`- VMFP_basff(c,a,r)*[pms(c,r) + qfm(c,a,r) + tfm(c,a,r)+if{a in fuelsect,`

`tfmghg(c,a,r)}]}`;

Equation `E_del_Vto_ffB` determines total collected revenues from subsidies to compensate FF input taxes:

Equation `E_del_Vto_ffB`

# Output tax/subsidy collected from ff targets #

`(all,a,AGRI_ACTS)(all,r,REG)`

`100*del_Vto_ff(a,r)=MAKEB_ff2(a,r)*to_ff2(a,r)+sum{c, COMM,[`

`MAKEB_ff(c,a,r)*{ps(c,a,r)+qca(c,a,r)+to(c,a,r)}-`

`MAKEB_to(c,a,r)*{ps(c,a,r)+qca(c,a,r)+to(c,a,r)}]}`;

Equation `E_del_ffslack` controls of FF taxes are collected and redistributed back to the producers (by exogenizing `del_ffslack(a,r)`).

Equation `E_del_ffslack`

# Controlling budget neutrality #

`(all,a,ACTS)(all,r,REG)`

`del_Vto_ff(a,r) = -del_Vtfa_ff(a,r) + del_ffslack(a,r);`

The simulations using this code, however showed that the taxes required to reduce the environmentally sensitive inputs are unrealistically high and sometimes the solution hasn't been found at all. There are two key reasons for this: i) the possibilities of substituting the required reduction of inputs is limited, particularly if pesticide is not split out of the chemical sector and is treated as a fixed input in the production (Leontief), and ii) the potential technologies that would allow to phase-out environmentally sensitive inputs without price interventions are not considered here.





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